

INFORMATION NEEDS AND INFORMATION SEEKING BEHAVIOR OF FACULTY MEMBERS OF AGRICULTURAL UNIVERSITIES IN BANGLADESH: A STUDY

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Abstract:

Information seeking is an impressive challenge and it is one of a substantial issue for Information Science. This study was undertaken to determine the information seeking behavior and library use by faculty members at the Agricultural University in Bangladesh. The overall purpose of the study was to determine what their information requirements and also determine their purpose of library services available for them in the library. The study collected data on the information requirements of faculty members. Data were gathered from 600 faculty members out of 905 through open and closed questionnaire. Findings indicate that guidance in the use of library resources and services are necessary to help them meet some of their information requirements. Finding also their seeking problems, using searching tools and level of satisfaction overall resources and services.

Keyword: Information Needs, Seeking Behavior, Agriculture, and Resources.

Introduction: The information use is a behavior that leads an individual to the use of information in order to need his/her information needs. Information use in an indicator of information needs, but they are not identical. Any individual do not use all the information they need. Information behavior is a broad term and encompassing the ways individuals articulate their information need, seek, evaluate and use information. In other words, information seeking behavior is purposive in nature and conspires of a need to satisfy some goal. The information seeking behavior of the faculty members as well as their information needs i.e., the information which is being sought may vary according to the age, sex, education, profession etc. So, the function of the libraries and the information seeking behavior of the users are to be correlated very carefully.

Information seeking behavior involves the searching, locating, retrieving and using of information. This process is influenced by the personality, emotionality variable, and educational variables and demographical variables of the person who seeks information. The information searching and acquisition process has several components such as passive attention, passive search, active search and ongoing search (Aaker, et al, 1992). The faculty members contribute to the attainment of the broad objectives of the universities: teaching, research and community service. Faculty members provide academic guidance to students and extents the frontiers of knowledge through research and publication.

Academic libraries in universities are prominent information organizations and play a crucial role in fulfilling the information needs of faculty members in different disciplines. The information needs of the faculty members of public universities have become complex and problematic due to the tremendous publications and interdisciplinary researches that are being promoted at the level of higher education. The librarians working in these institutions should pay paramount importance to acquire appropriate and need based literature in those subjects to the utmost satisfaction of their teachers.

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Review of Related Literature

Information seeking is undertaken to identify a message that satisfies a perceived need (Wright and Guy, 1997). This activity may be actively or passively done when taking steps to satisfy a felt need (Ikoja-Odongo, 2002). On the other hand, Andersen (2002) noted that research on information seeking has looked at how individuals go about finding the materials that they need in order to satisfy information needs. It was therefore noted on this basis that a number of models had been developed in this respect such as Ellis' 1993 model, Eisenberg and Berkowitz's 1992 model, and Kuhlthau's 1992 model. These models have been applied in a number of instances to follow up the patterns used in seeking

information or to explain how information could be sought systematically. The literature of information seeking behaviour of faculty members available is greatly broad ranging.

Salman and Hasim (2008) report the descriptive findings of the study on internet usage by Malays living in Kota Bharu, Kelantana, and a semi-urban town in the North East of peninsular Malaysia. Their findings highlight that the nature of use of internet differs from younger to the older. Various factors may determine the information seeking behavior of an individual or a group of individuals.

Fatima and Ahmad (2008) have investigated the information seeking behavior of the college students. They study the purpose, for which information is required, the environment in which the user operates users' skill in identifying the needed information, channels and sources preferred for getting information, and barriers to information. The same type of study in India has been done by **Mahajan and Ahmad (2009)**.

Ansari and Kumar (2010) have observed the information seeking behavior of college faculty in Uttar Pradesh. They study on the type of information sources used, preference of information formats, importance and reasons for using certain information sources.

Gowda and Shivalingaiah (2010) have made a similar study on the researchers in the University Libraries in Karnataka. The

results show that there is a significant difference among the research scholars of various disciplines in the preferences of various channels of information, modes of literature search, purpose of visit to the library and time spent.

Ossai (2011) in her study on the utilization of information by the University of Benin law students found that most of the law students indicated that they heavily used library resources in the course of their academic programs. However her study also revealed that most of the law students had difficulty in locating and identifying suitable library information sources for case law, legislation and legal journal articles. Despite universal agreement about the importance of the “essential” layering function, little empirical work on the information seeking behavior of law students appears in either the legal education literature or the library and information science (LIS) literature.

Nicol and O'English (2012) in their study found students and faculty satisfaction with library services and information made available to them. Information seeking and satisfaction with the library services are studied by authors. They found that, faculty, like students, also report increased satisfaction with current library-provided online tools and resources, and the marked difference between the expectations of faculty and student users is an important one. Rising faculty expectations highlight the importance of strengthening communication and connection with faculty

users so that libraries can retain relevancy in the academic environment.

Natarajan (2012) describes about electronic resources (e-resources) and their different types. The information seeking behavior of students, researchers and faculty in the e-environment is discussed. The role of library professionals in making the e-resources available to different types of user community is discussed in detail. It has been concluded that e-resources helps for anytime availability and easy to access, which helps for the researchers to carry out the research on time.

The study by **Rupp-Serrano and Robbins (2013)** explores the information-seeking behavior of academic education faculty from twenty large public research universities. The investigation includes an examination of how frequently education faculty seeks or access information, how they stay up-to-date on current developments in the field. The study highlights about electronic sources. The faculty emphasizes the importance of electronic access to scholarly journals and library databases and the continuing value of books, both print and electronic, for meeting the information and research needs.

Concept of information

Information as concepts remains tangled in a loosely defined terminology. Yet, everyone has to deal with it in many ways throughout their life. The simple meaning of information in a restricted science is a sensible statement, opinion, fact, concept of ideas, or an association of statements,

opinions or ideas. According to Davis and Olson (1985) “information is data that has been processed into a form that is meaningful to the recipient and is of real or perceived value in current or prospective action or decisions”. McCreadie and Rice (1999) review concepts of information proposed over the last fifty years. The concepts are:

- i) Information as a representation of knowledge.
- ii) Information as data in the environment.
- iii) Information as part of the communication process.
- iv) Information as a resource or commodity.

Information is the crucial need of users. Information is also an essential ingredient to participate in the new ways of doing personal and academic activities. Timely availability of up to date and appropriate information will no doubt generate creativity in the users.

Concept of information seeking behavior

Information seeking behavior refers to those activities a person engages in when identifying his or her own need for information, searching for such information in any way and using or transferring of information. Information behavior is the totality of human behavior in relation to the sources and channels of information, including both active and passive information seeking and information use. Thus it includes face to face and online communication with others as well as the

passive reception of information (Wilson, 2000). Information seeking behavior involves personal reasons for seeking information, the kinds of information which are being sought and the ways and sources with which needed information is being sought (Leckie et al., 1996). Information seeking behavior is expressed in various forms, from reading printed material to research and experimentation. Scholars, students and faculties actively seek current information from the various media available in libraries, for example encyclopedias, journals and more currently, electronic media. Abels (2004) mentioned that the frequency of use of the ‘internet’ in 1998 to 2000 had greatly increased. The library, therefore, is the most widely used source of information available to literate societies. The librarian should be aware of what kind of information is being sought and how it can be obtained. Due to the rapidly escalating cost of purchasing and archiving printed scholarly journals and electronic media, the library has the duty to provide and maintain efficient services.

Model of Information Seeking Behavior

Ellis’s (1989) elaborated of the different behaviors involved in information seeking is not set out as a diagrammatic model and Ellis makes no claim to the effect that the different behaviors constitute of a single set of stages; indeed, he uses the term ‘features’ rather than ‘stages’.

These features are named and defined below:

Starting: the means employed by the user to begin seeking information, for example, asking some knowledgeable colleague;

Chaining: following footnotes and citations in known material or ‘forward’ chaining from known items through citation indexes;

Browsing: ‘semi-directed or semi-structured searching’ of primary and secondary information;

Differentiating: using known differences in information sources as a way of filtering the amount of information obtained;

Monitoring: keeping up-to-date or current awareness searching;

Extracting: selectively identifying relative material in an information source;

Verifying: checking the accuracy of information;

Ending: this may be defined as ‘trying up loose ends’ through a final search.

Objectives

The major objectives of the study are to find out:

1. To identify the faculty members with their frequency of library visit.
2. To indicate the time spent in the library
3. To find out the purposes of information seeking.
4. To use of formal information resources

5. To utilize search engines by faculty members
6. To locate required information by using tools
7. To point out the problem faced their library resources.
8. To determine the level of satisfaction

Research Design and Data Collection

The study is based on the questionnaire survey, prepared after reviewing the related literature. The questionnaire was containing both open and close ended questions. Respondents included only the full-time faculty members of Agricultural Universities in Bangladesh. There are three agricultural universities and are having totaled 905 faculty members.

Random sampling technique was used in the study. Eighty five (85) faculty members had gone to aboard for higher study out of 905. A total of 820 questionnaires were distributed to the faculty members among three agricultural universities. Out of which 164 questionnaires were rejected due to incomplete, 56 questionnaires were not respondent and 600 questionnaires have been taken into account for the study. The collected data from the respondents, the data were checked and analyzed according to the objectives.

S#	Universities	Respondents of Faculty Members				Total
		Professors	Assoc. Prof.	Asst. Prof.	Lecturers	
01	Bangladesh Agricultural University (BAU)	172	72	76	65	385
02	Sher-e-Bangla Agricultural University(SAU)	25	18	30	24	97
03.	Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujibur Rahman Agricultural University (BSMRAU)	36	16	46	20	118
	Total	233	106	152	109	600

Frequently visit of library

It is noted from Table-1 that library daily 121(31%) and twice in a week 113(29%) are visited out of 385 respectively by faculty members in Bangladesh Agricultural University. SAU library is visited daily 28 (29%) and once in a week 39(40%) faculty

members out of 97 respectively. BSMRAU library is visited daily 48 (41%) and once in a week 31 (26%) by faculty members out of 118 respectively. It is mentioned that the library frequently visit in daily than other visit by all university's faculty members for their teaching and research purpose.

Table-1

Universities	Categories of Faculty Members	Frequently visit of library					Total	Percentage
		Daily	Once in a week	Twice in a week	Three times in a week	Occasionally		
BAU	Professors	45	38	42	22	25	172	44.68%
	Assoc. Profs.	21	27	16	07	01	72	18.70%
	Asst. Profs.	30	26	15	05	-	76	19.74%
	Lecturers	25	22	15	03	-	65	16.88%
	Total	121(31%)	113 (29%)	88 (23%)	37 (10%)	26 (07%)	385	100
SAU	Professors	07	10	05	03	-	25	25.77%
	Assoc. Profs.	04	10	03	01	-	18	18.56%
	Asst. Profs.	12	09	07	02	-	30	30.93%
	Lecturers	12	10	02	-	-	24	24.74%
	Total	28 (29%)	39 (40)	17 (18%)	06 (06%)	-	97	100
BSMRAU	Professors	10	15	08	03	-	36	30.51%
	Assoc. Prof.	05	03	07	01	-	16	13.56%
	Asst. Prof.	22	10	08	06	-	46	38.98%
	Lecturers	11	03	05	02	-	20	16.95%
	Total	48 (41%)	31(26%)	28(24%)	12 (10%)	-	118	100

Hours spent in the library

It is evident from Table-2 that 145(38%) and 136 (35%) out of 385 faculty members of BAU frequently spent their time in library at two and three hours respectively. 52 (54%) and 27 (28%) out of 97 faculty members spent their frequently maximum time in the

SAU library. Similarly, 57 (48.31%) and 34 (28.81%) out of 118 faculty members also frequently spent their time in BSMRAU library. It is good seen to utilize library resources by faculty members for their innovation research and bring new product from their research result. It is also

mentioned that Bangladesh is depended on agricultural products and gradually growing

up in this regard.

Table-2

Universities	Categories of Faculty Members	Frequently time spent in the library				Total	Percentage
		Less than one hour	Two hours	Three hours	More than five hours		
BAU	Professors	46	55	52	19	172	44.68%
	Assoc. Prof.	18	30	24	-	72	18.70%
	Asst. Prof.	11	35	30	-	76	19.74%
	Lecturers	10	25	30	-	65	16.88%
	Total	85 (22%)	145 (38%)	136 (35%)	19 (05%)	385	100
SAU	Professors	05	14	05	-	25	25.77%
	Assoc. Prof.	03	10	05	-	18	18.56%
	Asst. Prof.	04	15	09	02	30	30.93%
	Lecturers	03	13	08	-	24	24.74%
	Total	15 (15%)	52 (54%)	27 (28%)	02 (02%)	97	100
BSMRAU	Professors	13	17	06	-	36	30.51%
	Assoc. Prof.	02	08	06	-	16	13.56%
	Asst. Prof.	10	20	16	-	46	38.98%
	Lecturers	02	12	06	-	20	16.95%
	Total	27(22.88%)	57(48.31%)	34(28.81%)	-	118	100

Purpose of seeking Information

It is apparent from Table-3 that the majority of the respondents seeking information for the purpose of the career development 118 (30.65%). 104 (27.01%) to keep up-to-date, 80 (20.78%) to solve practical problem out of 385 of faculty members of BAU. To keep up-to-date 44 (45.36%), to solve practical problems 22 (22.68%) and 17

(17.53%) to develop career out of 97 Faculty members are seeking information from SAU library. Similarly, the faculty members of BSMRAU is seeking information for the purpose to keep up-to-date 51(43.22%), to write articles 19(16.10%), to development career 22 (18.64%) out of 118. It is proved that the faculty members are trying to develop their carrier and immediate solve the problems in research.

Table-3

Universities	Categories of Faculty Members	Purpose of seeking information					Total	Percentage (%)
		To keep up-to-date	To write article	To prepare class lecture	To solve practical problem	For career development		
BAU	Professors	56	15	13	45	43	172	44.68%

	Assoc. Prof.	16	10	06	15	25	72	18.70%
	Asst. Prof.	20	11	07	16	22	76	19.74%
	Lecturers	12	15	06	04	28	65	16.88%
	Total	104 (27.01%)	51(13.25%)	32 (8.31%)	80 (20.78%)	118(30.65)	385	100
SAU	Professors	12	1	-	12	-	25	25.77%
	Assoc. Prof.	10	-	-	05	03	18	18.56%
	Asst. Prof.	12	05	-	05	08	30	30.93%
	Lecturers	10	04	05	-	06	24	24.74%
	Total	44 (45.36%)	10 (10.31%)	05 (5.15%)	22 (22.68%)	17(17.53%)	97	100
BSMRAU	Professors	13	-	02	16	04	36	30.51%
	Assoc. Prof.	06	03	-	01	06	16	13.56%
	Asst. Prof.	16	12	10	-	08	46	38.98%
	Lecturers	12	04	-	-	04	20	16.95%
	Total	51(43.22%)	19(16.10%)	12 ((10.17%)	17(14.41%)	22(18.64%)	118	100

To use of formal information resources

Information sources depend on users' interest and demand in several disciplines of this study. Faculty members are seeking information from various sources to meet their needs during research and teaching purpose. From Table-4, it can be pointed out that majority of the respondents used information resources were books 171(44%), reference books 119(31%) and

periodicals 37(10%) of BAU library. Books 41(42%), reference books 33(34%) and other sources used by the faculty members of SAU in their library. In BSMRAU library, the faculty members used information sources are 49(42%), 40(34%), periodical 16(14%) and other sources are also using for research and teaching purpose.

Table-4

Universities	Categories of Faculty Members	Use of formal information sources						Total	Percentage
		Books	Periodicals	Reference sources	Thesis and project report	Conference proceeding	Annual Report		
BAU	Professors	65	15	45	17	15	15	172	44.68%
	Assoc. Prof.	31	10	25	6	-	-	72	18.70%
	Asst. Prof.	35	12	24	5	-	-	76	19.74%
	Lecturers	40	-	25	-	-	-	65	16.88%
	Total	171 (44%)	37 (10%)	119 (31%)	28(7%)	15(4%)	15 (4%)	385	100
SAU	Professors	12	02	08	02	01	-	25	25.77%
	Assoc. Prof.	07	02	07	01	01	-	18	18.56%
	Asst. Prof.	12	03	10	03	02	-	30	30.93%
	Lecturers	10	02	08	02	02	-	24	24.74%
	Total	41(42%)	09 (9%)	33 (34%)	08 (8%)	06(6%)	-	97	100

BSMRAU	Professors	15	05	12	02	02	-	36	30.51%
	Assoc. Prof.	08	01	06	-	-	01	16	13.56%
	Asst. Prof.	16	10	14	02	02	-	46	38.98%
	Lecturers	10	-	08	02	-	-	20	16.95%
	Total	49(42%)	16(14%)	40(34%)	06(5%)	04(3%)	01(1%)	118	100

To utilize of search engines

In the age of IT software program users can search documents for specific keywords and using Boolean operators for getting relevant documents from the web to save time of the users. Search engines are really sophisticated programs, the term is often used to specifically describe systems like Google, Yahoo, and AltaVista etc. But from the respondents only Google and Yahoo used to searching purpose and other search

engines are not used to search for getting their documents. Table-5 reveals that Google 222(58%) and Yahoo 163(42%) used for searching purpose out of 385 faculty members in BAU library. The faculty members of SAU used search engines Google 59(61%) and Yahoo 38(39%) out of 97 respectively. Similarly, Google 70(59%) and Yahoo 48(41%) are used search engines in their library by the faculty members of BSMRAU.

Table-5

Universities	Categories of Faculty Members	Use of different search engines					Total	Percentage
		Alta vista	Google	Yahoo	Rediff	Hobbot		
BAU	Professors	-	90	82	-	-	172	44.68%
	Assoc. Prof.	-	45	37	-	-	72	18.70%
	Asst. Prof.	-	51	25	-	-	76	19.74%
	Lecturers	-	36	29	-	-	65	16.88%
	Total	-	222(58%)	163(42%)	-	-	385	100
SAU	Professors	-	16	09	-	-	25	25.77%
	Assoc. Prof.	-	10	08	-	-	18	18.56%
	Asst. Prof.	-	17	13	-	-	30	30.93%
	Lecturers	-	16	08	-	-	24	24.74%
	Total	-	59(61%)	38(39%)	-	-	79	100
BSMRAU	Professors	-	20	16	-	-	36	30.51%
	Assoc. Prof.	-	10	06	-	-	16	13.56%
	Asst. Prof.	-	28	18	-	-	46	38.98%
	Lecturers	-	12	08	-	-	20	16.95%
	Total	-	70(59%)	48(41%)	-	--	118	100

To locate the required information by using tools

Agricultural university libraries in Bangladesh have vast collections to meet the need of faculty members in order to enhance research and teaching purpose in different fields of arena. Faculty members finding a particular item of information from vast collections but it is not easy to find without search patterns or tools. Library materials are logically and systematically arranged so that users can find out their required resources from vast collections. There are various tools to find a document of information from the library.

From **Table-6** that most of the respondents searched the information shelf search 127(32.99%), OPAC 92(23.385), card catalogue 80(20.78%) and help from other tools out of 385 faculty members respectively in BAU. The faculty members of SAU search shelf 37(38.17%), OPAC 35(36.08%) and help from other tools out of 97 faculty members for getting their information. BSMRAU faculty members searched their information using tools by search shelf 42(35.59%), OPAC 33(27.97%), card catalogue 31(26.27%) and other tools for getting required information from vast collections of the library.

Table-6

Universities	Categories of Faculty Members	Used different searching tools to locate information					Total	Percentage
		Shelf search	Card Catalogue	OPAC	Library staff	Library database		
BAU	Professors	45	25	50	40	12	172	44.68%
	Assoc. Prof.	25	20	12	10	05	72	18.70%
	Asst. Prof.	32	25	10	09	-	76	19.74%
	Lecturers	25	10	20	10	-	65	16.88%
	Total	127(32.99%)	80(20.78%)	92(23.38%)	69(17.92%)	17(4.41%)	385	100
SAU	Professors	10	-	10	05	-	25	25.77%
	Assoc. Prof.	06	02	05	05	-	18	18.56%
	Asst. Prof.	11	07	10	02	-	30	30.93%
	Lecturers	10	04	10	-	-	24	24.74%
	Total	37(38.17%)	13(13.40%)	35(36.08%)	12(12.37%)	-	97	100
MSMRAU	Professors	12	11	10	03	-	36	30.51%
	Assoc. Prof.	05	03	06	02	-	16	13.56%
	Asst. Prof.	21	12	10	03	-	36	38.98%
	Lecturers	04	05	07	02	02	20	16.95%
	Total	42(35.59%)	31(26.27%)	33(27.97%)	10(8.47%)	02(1.69%)	118	100

Problems faced in getting the required information

Information providers are always trying to meet fulfill the need of information seekers in the library. Moreover, It is seen overall libraries some lacking being in the library due to various reasons. **Table-7** indicates that lack of time 182(30.33%), inadequate collection 134(22.33%) and overload information 136 (22.67%) were problems

seriously faced by the faculty members at the time of getting their required documents in the library. Lacking 82(13.67%) and poor library facilities were also other faced problems in the library. Library collection development depends on teachers requisition at all, since they teach to the students in the class. They are also played prime duty to develop collection and inform to the authority their needs with the help of the library committee.

Table-7

Universities	Categories of Faculty Members	Problems faced in getting the information					Total	Percentage
		Lack of time	Inadequate collection	Overload information	Lack of knowledge	Poor library facilities		
BAU	Professors	40	25	45	35	27	172	44.68%
	Assoc. Prof.	25	20	21	-	06	72	18.70%
	Asst. Prof.	30	22	20	04	-	76	19.74%
	Lecturers	16	20	10	12	07	65	16.88%
	Total	111	87	96	51	40	385	100
SAU	Professors	07	05	08	-	05	25	25.77%
	Assoc. Prof.	06	-	05	05	-	18	18.56%
	Asst. Prof.	12	08	04	04	02	30	30.93%
	Lecturers	10	05	03	04	02	24	24.74%
	Total	35	18	20	13	09	97	100
BSMRAU	Professors	12	09	06	03	06	36	30.51%
	Assoc. Prof.	05	03	04	04	-	16	13.56%
	Asst. Prof.	13	12	05	10	06	46	38.98%
	Lecturers	06	04	05	-	05	20	16.95%
	Total	36	28	20	17	17	118	100
03	Total	182(30.33%)	134(22.33%)	136(22.67%)	82(13.67%)	66(11%)	600	100

Level of satisfaction regarding library resources and services

User satisfaction level depends on proper services, adequate collection and serene environment of the library. User expectation

cannot measure to provide services by library staff. In **Table-8** it is noted that most of the respondents have fully satisfied 307(51.16%) and partially satisfied 193(32.17%) on library collection, facilities, services, attitudes, library staff, infrastructure, library working time and

library procedures. As well as dissatisfied 100 (16.67%) is observed in library. Library lacking is possible to overcome through the level of satisfaction if adequate collection and library service provide properly to the users’.

Table-8

Universities	Categories of Faculty Members	Problems faced in getting the information				
		Fully satisfied	Partially satisfied	Dissatisfied	Total	Percentage
BAU	Professors	90	50	32	172	44.68%
	Assoc. Prof.	32	30	10	72	18.70%
	Asst. Prof.	45	25	06	76	19.74%
	Lecturers	30	25	10	65	16.88%
	Total	197	130	58	385	100
SAU	Professors	12	08	05	25	25.77%
	Assoc. Prof.	10	05	03	18	18.56%
	Asst. Prof.	14	10	06	30	30.93%
	Lecturers	14	06	04	24	24.74%
	Total	50	29	18	97	100
BSMRAU	Professors	16	12	08	36	30.51%
	Assoc. Prof.	07	05	04	16	13.56%
	Asst. Prof.	25	12	09	46	38.98%
	Lecturers	12	05	03	20	16.95%
	Total	60	34	24	118	100
03	Total	307(51.16%)	193(32.17%)	100(16.67%)	600	100

Suggestions: The significance of information as a vital resource in every sphere of life emphasizes the information needs of the people and thoughts together. The information needs and information seeking behavior differ from person to person. Based on the analysis of data and observation of the result, to enhance the effectiveness of information seeking behavior and to promote the utilization of information services in the university libraries so that users can be satisfied to

getting required information in time. The following suggestions and recommendation have been made.

1. The top priorities should be given for providing current documents so that respondents can save their time in order to have better research and teaching by the libraries.
2. To make sure as potential services to the users meet their

immediate information needs very quickly, effectively and efficiently.

3. Agricultural libraries in Bangladesh should be well-equipped with modern gadgets such as computer, internet, fax machine, standard software, web facilities in the library.
4. Rare issues of journals, newspaper, thesis, dissertations, FAO publications etc. should be converted into electronic format and could be made easily accessible to the users.
5. Professionally trained staff should be employed and existing staff should be send for training by which they handle effectively for providing better services to their user community sincerely.
6. Library staff should organize user education programme within the library to facilitate the users to make full use of the library services and resources at regular interval.
7. Library day programme should be launched in a year within the seminar hall of the library so that new comer and less frequent users of library helpful and acquaintances with resources as well facilities.
8. Recommended library hours and collection should increase according to users' expectation/

demand of three agricultural universities in Bangladesh.

Conclusion: The core of the library profession remains the same but methods and tools for information delivery continue to grow and change dramatically with the help ICT. Every Library must understand information-seeking behavior of users to re-engineer their services and provide information efficiently. The results of this study reveal users are satisfied with library collections and services, but who want training in the use of online information. Although document delivery service is being provided on demand, the researchers pointed out that it would be worthwhile if the library could provide them with indexing, abstracting and interlibrary loan service as well. The successful operation of a library depends to a large extent on the choice of library collections. The collection should meet the needs and requirements of users. Consequently, librarians must be aware of how faculty seeks information. Knowledge of faculty information needs and information-seeking behavior is imperative for developing valuable collections, and improving facilities and services. It is recommended that library staff or reference librarians focus on assisting users to develop a better image for the library. Reference librarians should help teachers improve their information-seeking and find the types of information they need. User education about library using should be carried out as a seminar or workshop training.

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